

DYNAMICS OF PHYSICAL HEALTH OF STUDENTS WITH DIFFERENT REGIMES OF MOTOR ACTIVITY DURING STUDY AT A MEDICAL UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The problem of forming, maintaining and strengthening the health of the population is one of the priority tasks of the state, recognized as a factor of national security, stability and well-being of society. Particular attention is paid to the health of student youth. Purpose: to conduct an integral assessment of the health status of students with different modes of physical activity..

Aim: The problem of forming, maintaining and strengthening the health of the population is one of the priority tasks of the state, recognized as a factor of national security, stability and well-being of society. Particular attention is paid to the health of student youth. Purpose: to conduct an integral assessment of the health status of students with different modes of physical activity.

Materials and methods: The study was conducted based on the results of prospective observations of the physical health of 1500 3rd year students (628 boys and 872 girls) during the 2023-2025 academic year. In the course of the study, a student's medical control card was filled out, including sections: passport part (questionnaire data on

conditions and lifestyle, past diseases); anthropometric data (body length (BL), body weight (BW), chest circumference, dynamometry, spirometry); external examination data; data of the nearest sports anamnesis; data from the examination of internal organs; assessment of physical development (methods of indices and standards); results of functional tests (Stange, Genchi, Serkin, Martine tests, vegetative tests, Harvard step test).

Results: According to sports anamnesis: the majority of students have never played sports, 30% have previously played sports, 10% of students continue to play sports regularly. When studying physical development (PhD): 65% of students have moderately harmonious PhD, 10% - below average disharmonious, 20% - above average harmonious, 5% - low disharmonious PhD. According to functional tests: according to respiratory tests, the

following results were obtained: in 52% of students, the physical condition of the respiratory system is normal, where reduced indicators were registered in 58% of students.

According to the results of Martine tests: normotonic type of reaction of the cardiovascular system (CVS) was registered in 58% of students, hypertonic - 21%, dystonic - 21%, hypotonic type was not observed in students. When assessing the vegetative status according to orthostatic, clinorthostatic tests and vegetative indexes of Kerdo-Kardyu: 78% have normotonic, 22% - sympathicotonic. When assessing physical fitness using the Harvard step test, it was revealed that only 1% of students had good and excellent physical fitness, while 55% of students had below average fitness, 25% had an average fitness level, and 20% had a poor fitness level.

Conclusions: Thus, among the 3rd year students, low physical activity was revealed, which is expressed in the following indicators: low value of the cardio-respiratory system, sympathicotonia and low levels of physical fitness. The results obtained dictate the need to create conditions for increasing the physical activity of students

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